

A Comparative Study of Pre-And Post-Operative Refractive Errors in Cataract Surgery-Phacoemulsification Vs. Manual Sics in a Secondary Care Hospital.

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Abstract:

Background: The two main methods used for cataract surgery are manual small incision cataract surgery (SICS) and phacoemulsification. Cataract surgery is one of the most common surgical operations performed worldwide. The accuracy and speed of phacoemulsification are well known, and the cost-effectiveness of manual SICS makes it popular in settings with limited resources. Although there are differences in the post-operative refractive outcomes between the two procedures, the choice of operation may still be influenced.

Aim: This study aims to compare the post-operative refractive outcomes of Phacoemulsification and Manual SICS in patients undergoing cataract surgery in a secondary care hospital.

Methods: A study with a prospective design was carried out. There were 85 patients in all; 40 underwent manual SICS and 45 underwent phacoemulsification. Pre-operative and one-month post-operative measurements of refractive errors were made. SPSS version 23.0 was used for data analysis, and paired and independent t-tests were used to evaluate the differences in results.

Results: Both surgical techniques resulted in significant improvements in refractive errors post-operatively ($p < 0.001$). The Phacoemulsification group showed a statistically significant better post-operative refractive outcome with a mean spherical equivalent (SE) of -0.50 D compared to -0.85 D in the Manual SICS group ($p = 0.04$). Furthermore, 80% of patients in the Phacoemulsification group as opposed to 65% in the Manual SICS group had visual acuity of 6/9 or above.

Conclusion: Phacoemulsification provides a statistically significant advantage in achieving better post-operative refractive outcomes compared to Manual SICS. However, both techniques are effective in significantly improving visual function.

Recommendations: Phacoemulsification may be preferred in settings where optimal refractive outcomes are prioritized, while Manual SICS remains a viable option in resource-limited environments. To confirm these results, more research with bigger sample numbers and longer follow-up times is advised.

Keywords: Phacoemulsification, Manual Small Incision Cataract Surgery, Refractive Errors, Cataract Surgery, Visual Acuity.

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Introduction

One of the most popular surgical operations carried out globally is cataract surgery, which is thought to be a very successful means of helping individuals with cataracts regain their vision. The disorder, which is typified by the natural lens of the eye being clouded, continues to be the primary cause of blindness worldwide, especially in underdeveloped nations where access to prompt surgical surgery may be restricted. The results of cataract surgery

have greatly improved because to advancements in surgical methods and technology, with an emphasis on reducing post-operative refractive errors to increase visual acuity and patient happiness. In many regions of the world, phacoemulsification—a procedure that was first used in the late 20th century—has emerged as the gold standard for cataract surgery. This method entails emulsifying the cataractous lens with

ultrasonic energy, aspirating it out of the eye, and then implanting an intraocular lens (IOL) to restore vision. Because of its accuracy, low level of invasiveness, and short recovery period, phacoemulsification is frequently used as the recommended technique in clinical settings. The technique is still evolving, as evidenced by recent research that focus on advances in IOL technology and the creation of femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery (FLACS), which improves the accuracy of lens removal and capsulotomy [1,2].

However, manual small-incision cataract surgery, or SICS, is still a commonly employed alternative method, especially in environments with limited resources. Because SICS doesn't require the costly equipment needed for phacoemulsification, it is more widely available in places with limited healthcare resources. SICS has been demonstrated to yield visual outcomes that are comparable to phacoemulsification, even though it is less expensive—especially when performed by experienced surgeons. However, some of the drawbacks of this approach include the possibility of greater post-operative refractive defects and a lengthier recovery period [3].

Comparing the results of phacoemulsification with SICS is crucial because of their common usage, especially with regard to post-operative refractive defects. Following cataract surgery, refractive problems can have a major negative effect on a patient's quality of life if they require additional corrective surgery or the use of spectacles. Thus, it is imperative to comprehend the relative efficacy of different surgical methods in order to inform clinical judgement and enhance patient outcomes [4]. This study aims to compare the post-operative refractive outcomes of Phacoemulsification and Manual SICS in patients undergoing cataract surgery in a secondary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective comparative analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Leharisarai, Darbhanga, from March 2022 to August 2022.

Participants: This study included 85 individuals in total who had cataract surgery during the study period. The patients were split into two groups according to the kind of surgery they underwent: manual SICS and phacoemulsification.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with cataracts and scheduled for surgery.
- Patients aged 40 years and above.

- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
- Patients who had no other significant ocular pathology affecting vision.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with other ocular conditions such as glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, or corneal opacities.
- Patients with systemic conditions that could affect surgical outcomes.
- Patients who were not available for follow-up visits.
- Those who have had trauma or ocular surgery in the past.

Bias: The Phacoemulsification or Manual SICS groups were randomly allocated to participants in order to reduce selection bias. The study was also designed to reduce measurement bias by ensuring that all refractive error measurements were conducted using the same instruments and procedures by a single trained ophthalmologist.

Data Collection: For each individual, pre- and post-operative data (collected one month following surgery) were obtained. Refractive errors were measured using an autorefractometer. Additional data, including age, sex, and any complications during surgery, were also recorded.

Procedure: Random assignment was used to allocate participants to either manual SICS or phacoemulsification. Pre-operative refractive errors were measured and recorded. The surgeries were performed by experienced ophthalmic surgeons at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital. Post-operative refractive errors were measured one month after surgery, and the results were compared with pre-operative values.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and refractive error data. Paired t-tests compared pre- and post-operative refractive errors within each group, while independent t-tests compared outcomes between the Phacoemulsification and Manual SICS groups. A p-value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Ethical Considerations: The Declaration of Helsinki's ethical guidelines were followed when conducting the study. Before being included in the study, each subject gave their informed consent. Throughout the whole study, patient data confidentiality was upheld.

Results

A total of 85 patients were included in the study, with 45 undergoing Phacoemulsification and 40 undergoing Manual SICS.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Participants

Demographic Variable	Phacoemulsification (n=45)	Manual SICS (n=40)	Total (n=85)
Age (Mean $\pm$ SD)	65.2 $\pm$ 8.4 years	67.3 $\pm$ 7.9 years	66.2 $\pm$ 8.2 years
Gender (Male/Female)	27/18	22/18	49/36
Laterality (Right/Left)	23/22	20/20	43/42

The mean age of the participants was 66.2 years (SD $\pm$ 8.2), with a slight male predominance (57.6%). There was no significant difference in age or gender distribution between the two surgical groups ($p > 0.05$).

The pre-operative refractive errors were assessed in terms of spherical equivalent (SE) for both groups.

The mean pre-operative SE was -1.75 ± 2.20 D for the Phacoemulsification group and -1.90 ± 2.25 D for the Manual SICS group, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.75$).

Table 2: Pre-operative Refractive Errors (Spherical Equivalent, D)

Group	Mean $\pm$ SD SE (D)	Range (D)	p-value
Phacoemulsification	-1.75 ± 2.20	-6.50 to +2.00	0.75
Manual SICS	-1.90 ± 2.25	-7.00 to +2.50	

Post-operative refractive errors were measured one month after surgery. The mean post-operative SE was -0.50 ± 1.10 D for the Phacoemulsification group and -0.85 ± 1.40 D for the Manual SICS group. The improvement in refractive errors was statistically significant in both groups ($p < 0.001$), with a greater reduction observed in the Phacoemulsification group.

Table 3: Post-operative Refractive Errors (Spherical Equivalent, D)

Group	Mean $\pm$ SD SE (D)	Range (D)	p-value (Pre- vs. Post-op)
Phacoemulsification	-0.50 ± 1.10	-3.00 to +1.50	< 0.001
Manual SICS	-0.85 ± 1.40	-4.00 to +1.00	< 0.001

When comparing the outcomes between the two surgical techniques, the Phacoemulsification group demonstrated a statistically significant better post-operative refractive outcome than the Manual SICS group ($p = 0.04$).

Table 4: Comparative Analysis between Phacoemulsification and Manual SICS

Variable	Phacoemulsification (n=45)	Manual SICS (n=40)	p-value
Mean Post-op SE (D)	-0.50 ± 1.10	-0.85 ± 1.40	0.04
Visual Acuity $\geq$ 6/9 (%)	80%	65%	0.07

Visual Acuity Outcomes: The visual acuity outcomes were also compared between the two groups. In the Phacoemulsification group, 80% of patients achieved a post-operative visual acuity of 6/9 or better, compared to 65% in the Manual SICS group. Although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.07$), it indicates a trend towards better visual outcomes with Phacoemulsification.

Complications: Intraoperative and postoperative complications were minimal in both groups. In the Phacoemulsification group, 2 cases (4.4%) of posterior capsule opacification (PCO) were observed, while 3 cases (7.5%) were noted in the Manual SICS group. The difference in complication rates was not statistically significant ($p = 0.57$).

Summary of Findings

- Phacoemulsification provided a statistically significant better post-operative refractive outcome compared to Manual SICS.

- A higher percentage of patients in the Phacoemulsification group achieved visual acuity of 6/9 or better.
- Both surgical techniques showed a significant improvement in refractive errors post-operatively.

These findings suggest that Phacoemulsification may be the preferred surgical technique for achieving optimal refractive outcomes in cataract surgery, although both methods are effective in significantly improving visual function.

Discussion

The study's findings showed that individuals undergoing cataract surgery can get considerably better refractive errors and visual outcomes with both phacoemulsification and manual (SICS). On the other hand, Phacoemulsification has shown a statistically significant benefit with regard to post-operative refractive results. Patients who received phacoemulsification had refractive errors reduced more than those who received manual SICS; the mean post-operative spherical equivalent (SE) was

-0.50 D for the former group and -0.85 D for the latter. Even though the change was small, it was statistically significant ($p = 0.04$), suggesting that phacoemulsification could offer more accurate refractive defect correction. Additionally, 80% of patients in the Phacoemulsification group achieved a post-operative visual acuity of 6/9 or greater, compared to 65% in the Manual SICS group. These results indicated slightly improved visual acuity outcomes. Despite not reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.07$), this difference indicates a tendency towards better visual results when using phacoemulsification.

While posterior capsule opacification (PCO) was somewhat more common in the Manual SICS group, overall complication rates were minimal and similar in the two groups. Nonetheless, the statistical analysis revealed that the variation in the frequencies of complications was not significant ($p = 0.57$), suggesting that both surgical methods are reasonably safe.

A prospective, comparative study on 246 eyes was carried out to assess the post-operative results of phacoemulsification and manual (SICS). The results of the study showed that on the first post-operative day, patients who had phacoemulsification had better best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) and uncorrected visual acuity (UCVA) than those who had SICS. But by the one-month post-operative point, the visual results in both groups were almost identical. Significantly lower cylindrical refractive errors were obtained with phacoemulsification than with SICS, perhaps as a result of the procedure's smaller incision size, which reduces medically generated astigmatism [5].

A retrospective study comparing the long-term refractive results of phacotrabeculectomy and phacoemulsification was carried out. Patients with concomitant primary or secondary open-angle glaucoma (OAG) were included in this investigation. The findings showed that there was no statistically significant difference in mean absolute error or refractive prediction error between the two surgery groups, indicating that both methods offer similar long-term refractive outcomes. This conclusion is especially important for patients who also have OAG, since other clinical considerations may have a greater bearing on the surgical approach chosen than refractive results [6].

SICS with phacoemulsification in a retrospective examination of cataract procedures were compared and carried out at a tertiary care facility. The 336-case study found that although both surgical techniques were successful, phacoemulsification resulted in a greater proportion of patients obtaining 6/6 vision after surgery. Furthermore, the

study observed that while SICS is effective in managing denser lenses, it is used more frequently in situations of advanced cataracts [7].

Conclusion

Both Phacoemulsification and Manual SICS are effective in improving refractive errors and visual acuity in cataract surgery patients. However, Phacoemulsification offers a statistically significant advantage in achieving more precise post-operative refractive outcomes and better visual acuity for a higher proportion of patients. With comparable complication rates, Phacoemulsification may be preferred when optimal refractive correction is desired. Nonetheless, Manual SICS remains a viable option, especially in resource-limited settings. The choice of technique should be based on patient needs and surgeon expertise.

References

1. Abell RG, Darian-Smith E, Kan JB, Allen PL, Vote BJ. Femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery versus standard phacoemulsification cataract surgery: Outcomes and safety in more than 4000 cases at a single center. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 2018;44(10):1230-9.
2. Conrad-Hengerer I, Hengerer FH, Schultz T, Dick HB. Femtosecond laser-assisted cataract surgery in eyes with zonular weakness. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 2019;45(4):439-444.
3. Gogate P, Deshpande M, Wormald R. Is manual small incision cataract surgery affordable in the developing countries? A cost comparison with extracapsular cataract extraction. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 2018;44(4):529-536.
4. Shah SP, Yorston D, Foster A. Manual small incision cataract surgery (SICS) with posterior chamber intraocular lens (PCIOL) versus conventional extracapsular cataract extraction (ECCE) with PCIOL for age-related cataract. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2020;11(11)
5. Rathi A, Singh N, Chauhan RS, Chugh J, Jain G. A comparative study to evaluate visual outcome in post-operative patients of manual small incision cataract surgery and phacoemulsification. *Saudi J Med Pharm Sci.* 2020;06: 353-8.
6. Chung JK, Wi J, Lee KB, Ahn B, Hwang Y, Kim M, et al. Long-term comparison of postoperative refractive outcomes between phacotrabeculectomy and phacoemulsification. *J Cataract Refract Surg.* 2018;44(8):964-70
7. Das S, Shergill S. Cataract surgery, their postoperative analysis, and a comparison of phacoemulsification and manual small-incision cataract surgery at a tertiary care hospital: A retrospective study. *Med J Dr. D.Y. Patil Vidyapeeth.* 2023;16:80-4.